

Examining Assertive Social Influence and Its Effect on Decision Making: An Experimental Approach

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Abstract

The study examines the influence of assertive social presence on the individual decision-making of first-year students enrolled in the university. In order to assess the students' decision-making during the pre-intervention and post-intervention, the study adopted a quasi-experimental design. Meanwhile, utilizing a within-subject design, the initial and final responses of the participants ($n=30$) were used for comparison. A Chi-Square test revealed no significant difference between the initial and final responses of ($p = 0.732$ for the Love Issue; $p = 0.869$ for the Obligation Issue). A manipulation check survey was conducted to assess the participants' perception of the assertive influence and showed a low perceived manipulation ($\bar{x}=2.42$, $SD=0.621$, $SE=0.113$). Based on the findings of the study, the assertive social presence did not significantly influence the decision-making of individuals. The generalizability of the study is constrained by its limited sample size and lack of demographic diversity. Confounding variables, including question format and unmeasured confidence levels, may have influenced results, while inadequate confederate assertiveness could affect validity. Future research may employ correlational or alternative designs to examine the impact of social influence on decision-making, alongside measuring confidence levels, exploring cultural values, incorporating diverse age groups, refining question formats, and increasing sample sizes to improve accuracy and generalizability.

Keywords: *Assertive Social Influence, Individual decision-making, Quasi-Experimental Design, Within-subject design.*

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Introduction

How would your personal decision change if someone in the group boldly disagreed with the majority while speaking in a powerful and strong voice? Would you embrace the prevailing opinion or stick with your initial viewpoint? This study investigates the dynamic relationship between decision-making and assertiveness, offering insight into the process that influences the social behaviour of a person.

Decision-making, according to Savioni et al. (2022), is the act of selecting one alternative from a range of options in order to achieve a desired goal. This procedure requires a careful evaluation of the alternatives provided as well as the application of reasoning and information-processing techniques to arrive at the best decision. However, societal factors are often involved, especially in a group setting, and decision-making is not always an autonomous process. As an example, people might feel influenced to comply with the choices made by those around them when they come across an assertive individual who respectfully and calmly communicates their desires and, at the same time, respects those of others (Oana, 2019).

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As defined by Chakraborty (2023), social conformity is the tendency of people to align their beliefs or behaviour with the norms of a group, usually due to explicit or implicit social influences. As per Sustein (2019), it is powerful and significantly affects how people behave in social contexts. This might result in groupthink and a decrease in an individual's ability for critical thinking. Wang (2024) cited Asch's (1951) study on conformity that investigated the influence of social pressure from a majority group on an individual's decision. Asch's study used confederates who intentionally gave incorrect answers on a line judgment task given to the participants; the intensity of social influence was evident, given that 32% of the participants selected the group's false response despite the fact that the correct answer was evident.

While conformity might promote group cohesion, it can also be harmful because it hinders individuality and promotes irrational decision-making. Fadilla's research in 2020 specifically examines how conformity influences career decision-making among students aged 13 to 18. This indicates that when students conform to peer pressure or group expectations, they might make choices that do not align with their true interests or aspirations. In addition, according to a local study by Logrosa (2021), cited in Pamaos et al. (2024), students in Region XI, specifically in Davao City, face major challenges when it comes to decision-making. Managing stress, striking a balance between academic responsibilities and personal goals, and managing social pressures that often lead to conformity were among these challenges.

On another note, previous research frequently concentrates on the subtle forms of influence, such as implicit (Ciranka & Van Den Bos, 2019) or passive persuasion (Laursen & Veenstra, 2021), overlooking the specific dynamics or assertive social influence in individual decision-making after a group discussion. In addition, although some research has looked at how people or groups make decisions (Suri, 2019), it usually ignores how decisions made by an individual go from independent choices to finalized options following group discussion, especially when an assertive influence is involved. Moreover, many studies ignore the slow changes in people's choices that take place when facing exposure to an assertive group. Instead, they focus more on the decisions made at the beginning or conclusion of group discussions (Damanik & Wening, 2024).

This research aimed to fill in these gaps by increasing the body of knowledge about how the presence of assertive individuals influences others' decision-making following group discussions, which might be useful within the field of organizational behaviour, social psychology, and leadership. It provides a solid foundation for deepening the public's understanding of the influence of assertive social presence and how it can shift norms, attitudes, and decisions in real-world settings.

Sutton (2021) defines assertive social influence as advocating for one's interests respectfully while considering the rights and viewpoints of others. The Social Influence Theory of Herbert Kelman (1950s) identifies three processes that examine how individuals' interactions with other people shape their attitudes, beliefs, and behaviours: compliance, identification, and internalization. Compliance involves adhering to group norms to gain acceptance, while identification occurs when individuals adopt behaviours of admired groups, and internalization reflects changes aligning with personal values (Wrench et al., 2021). According to Kelman, attitude and behaviour change result from individuals modifying their views and values in response to the new knowledge introduced by an influencing agent (Davlembayeva & Papagiannidis, 2024).

Materials and Methods

Research Design

The purpose of this experimental study was to evaluate how assertive social influence affected first-year university students' decision-making. In order to assess the students' decision-making tendencies during the pre-intervention and post-intervention, the study adopted a quasi-experimental design. This design aims to establish a cause-and-effect relationship but does not rely on random assignment in which subjects are assigned to groups based on a non-random criterion (Thomas, 2020). Additionally, a within-subject design was used, which allowed the same participants to be exposed to assertive social influence

under controlled conditions to test whether they were influenced by the assertive social presence after group discussion (Cruz-Khalili et al., 2019).

Participants

The researchers used a purposive random sampling design approach to ensure the participants selected were in line with the inclusion criteria, i.e., the characteristics needed by the researchers in this study (Nikolopoulou, 2022). This method was used to select thirty (30) first-year students from the university who were available within the experiment's scheduled duration.

The inclusion criteria required the individuals to be (1) enrolled at the University, (2) in their first year, (3) between the ages 18 and 25, (4) of any gender, and (5) available throughout the experiment to be eligible to participate in the study. Excluded were those individuals who (1) were not enrolled at the university, (2) were senior high school students, (3) were in their second, third, and fourth year, and (4) were unavailable during the experimental timeframe.

Instrument

The researchers recruited two confederates to assert their answers, which were purposely different from the group's responses, to test the assertive social influence. This was done to create an environment where the confederates' assertive social presence could potentially influence the decision-making of participants.

In order to gather data from the research participants, the researchers administered a survey. The survey, titled the Manipulation Check Survey, included four items and employed a 1-5 Likert scale to assess participants' perceptions about whether or not assertive social presence had an influence on them. Each numerical value on the Likert scale had a corresponding interpretation to evaluate the degree of influence experienced by the participants.

The first question of the Manipulation Check Survey asked, *"To what extent did you feel pressure to agree with the group?"* Participants evaluated the extent of pressure they felt to adhere to group ideas. A rating of 5 (very much) showed that they were under intense pressure to comply, whilst a rating of 1 (not at all) suggested that there was no such pressure. Intermediate scores of 4 (a lot), 3 (moderately), and 2 (a little) indicated varied levels of perceived pressure, ranging from primary to negligible.

To assess the influence of group opinions on individual decisions, participants were asked to rate how much they believed their choices were influenced by others. A rating of 5 (completely) indicated total influence, while a rating of 1 (not at all) indicated no influence at all. Responses of 4 (significantly), 3 (moderately), and 2 (slightly) indicated decreasing levels of influence.

Participants were also asked how nonverbal cues, such as body language and facial expressions, influenced their decisions. A rating of 4 (Yes, definitely) showed that such signals were evident and had a substantial influence, whereas 1 (No) meant no such cues were observed. Intermediate ratings of 3 (Yes, somewhat) and 2 (Yes, but minimally) reflected varied levels of awareness and influence over nonverbal actions.

For the last question, participants reflected on whether they thought their decisions would have been the same if done alone. A rating of 5 (Definitely yes) suggested confidence in making the same judgement independently, whereas 1 (Definitely not) implied that the decision would have been completely different. Ratings of 4 (probably yes), 3 (unsure), and 2 (probably not) exhibited a range of trust in the consistency of their decisions.

Lastly, the total mean scores of the participants were used to estimate the extent of perceived group influence. Values higher than 3.80 showed a strong impression of group influence, whilst values between 3.40 and 3.79 indicated a moderate perception. Scores less than 3.39 were classified as indicating a low amount of perceived impact.

Procedure

The researchers actively roamed around the campus looking for participants who fulfilled the study's inclusion requirements. Potential participants were verbally informed about the nature of the study, their rights as participants, and their role in the study. The participants were then asked to take two preference tests: "The One I Love or The One Who Loves Me" and "Do children feel obligated to give back to their family? Yes or No."

After the participants had completed answering the recruitment questionnaires, the researchers utilized a quasi-experimental design to assign participants to their designated sessions. A non-random criterion was applied, grouping participants based on their initial answers to the two preference questions. The sessions were structured as follows: participants who answered "The One Who Loves Me" and "Yes" were included in the first session; participants who answered "The One Who Loves Me" and "No" were included in the second session; and the third session was divided into two independent sessions: the first session involved participants who initially answered "The One I Love" and "Yes," and those who responded first with "The One I Love" and "No" were part of the second session. This design preserved the integrity of the study's goals while enabling the researchers to examine variations in responses depending on discrete categories.

After grouping, the participants were contacted via Messenger to inform them of their scheduled session of participation in the experiment, which was conducted on different days from 2:30 to 3:30 in the afternoon.

The first experimental session was held with nine (9) out of the thirty participants, who initially answered "The One Who Loves Me" and "Yes." Before the session began, the participants received an informed consent form containing their rights to voluntary participation, data confidentiality, potential for publication, and their right to withdraw from the study. Following this, participants were greeted warmly and briefed on the purpose of the study and the task they would be completing. The primary focus, the influence of assertive social influence, was purposely omitted, and the participants were only informed that they would be taking a preference test.

The session began with the participants being instructed to take seats in the chairs provided and were given the chance to introduce themselves and interact with others in the group. Afterward, two 1/16-sized pieces of paper were given to them to write their answers on. For the first preferential topic, "The One I Love or The One Who Loves Me," participants engaged in a five-minute group discussion before having ten seconds to write their answers. The process was repeated for the second question, "Do children feel obligated to give back to their family? Yes or no." In order to encourage assertive social influence, confederates, during the discussions, asserted opinions that contradicted the participants' initial choices, notably "The One I Love" and "No." After five minutes, participants were given another ten seconds to revise or confirm their answers to the question.

In the second experiment, the same methods were applied as in the initial experiment. For this session, a different set of participants was selected. Seven (7) participants who answered "The One Who Loves Me" and "No" were included in the session. The confederates asserted the concepts of "The One I Love" and "Yes" in contrast to the participants' initial responses during the group discussions. Similarly, the third experiment, which has two independent sessions, was carried out on the following day. The first session involved participants who initially answered "The One I Love" and "Yes," whereas the confederates maintained opposing viewpoints. The second session comprised participants who answered "The One I Love" and "No," following the same process with the confederates asserting contradictory views to promote social presence.

After the experiment, participants were provided with a survey questionnaire designed to evaluate their perspective on assertive social influence. Before concluding the session, the researchers had a debriefing, during which they disclosed the use of deception in the study—notably, the inclusion of assertive confederates – and clarified the true nature of the study, emphasizing the necessity of using deception.

Each participant was given a small memento of appreciation for their time and effort. The researchers then collected and arranged the data. To keep everything organized and protected from unauthorized access by individuals outside the researchers, the information is safely kept in an envelope.

Ethical Considerations

Throughout the course of the research, the researchers closely followed the ethical standards to safeguard the rights and welfare of the participants involved. Ethical considerations are essential in research as they not only safeguard participants' interests but also promote the credibility of the study. As Resnik (2020) emphasizes, adhering to ethical considerations promotes the aims of research and ensures that participants are treated with dignity and respect.

Informed Consent. The participants were given an informed consent form to read and sign prior to participating in the study. This explains the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, their right to withdraw, potential for publication, and confidentiality. The signed consent form served as a formal agreement for their involvement in the study.

Confidentiality. The researchers honour participants' privacy rights. This was specified in the informed consent form, which assures participants that their identities will only be accessible to the researchers and used solely for the purposes of the study.

Voluntary Participation. The participants were assured by the researchers that their involvement was entirely voluntary. Additionally, participants were informed that they were free to recede from the study at any point during the experiment without any negative repercussions.

Dissemination of Findings. Participants were informed that the study's findings might be published, with all data presented in aggregate to protect their anonymity.

Debriefing. In order to examine the influence of assertive social presence on individual decision-making, the researchers employed deception. After the experiment, a debriefing was conducted to address the ethical issues of this approach. Participants were informed and explained the true nature of the study, with the element of assertive social presence introduced in detail at this stage.

Results

Love Issue

Table 1. The Outcome of the Initial and Final Answers Regarding Love Issue

Final (Love Issue)				
Initial (Love Issue)		The One Who Loves Me	The One I Love	Total
The One Who Loves Me	Observed	9	7	16
	Expected	8.53	7.47	16
The One I Love	Observed	7	7	14
	Expected	7.47	6.53	14
Total	Observed	16	14	30
	Expected	16	14	30

Table 2. Goodness-of-Fit on Love Issue

X ²	df	p
0.117	1	0.732

X² Goodness-of-Fit test was conducted to examine the difference between participants' initial and final responses regarding love issues ("The One I Love" or "The One Who Loves Me"). The test revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between the observed and expected responses of the

participants, $\chi^2(1, N=30) = 0.117, p = 0.732$. Furthermore, participants changed their answers from “The One Who Loves Me” ($N=16$) to “The One I Love” ($N=7$), while from “The One I Love” ($N=14$) to “The One Who Loves Me” ($N=7$). This showed that the presence of assertive individuals during the group discussion did not significantly influence the participants’ answers and change their initial answers.

Obligation Issue

Table 3. The Outcome of the Initial and Final Answers Regarding Obligation Issue

Final (Obligation Issue)				
Initial (Obligation Issue)		NO	YES	Total
YES	Observed	14	3	17
	Expected	14.2	2.83	17.0
NO	Observed	11	2	13
	Expected	10.8	2.17	13.0
Total	Observed	25	5	30
	Expected	25	5	30

Table 4. Goodness-of-Fit on Obligation Issue

X ²	df	p
0.0271	1	0.869

X² Goodness-of-Fit test was conducted to examine whether the initial response of the participants was influenced during the discussion with the presence of assertive individuals on the question (Do children have an obligation to give back to their family?) That was answered by yes or no. The test revealed that the final answers of the participants were consistent with the expected frequencies $\chi^2(1, N=30) = 0.0271, p = 0.869$. In addition, participants changed their responses from Yes ($N=17$) to No ($N=14$), whereas from No ($N=11$) to Yes ($N=2$). This showed that the presence of assertive individuals during the group discussion did not significantly influence the participants’ answers and change their initial answers.

Level of Perceived Manipulation Among Participants

Table 5. Level of Perceived Manipulation Among Participants

	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE
Q1	30	2.17	2.0	0.986	0.180
Q2	30	2.47	2.0	1.074	0.196
Q3	30	2.30	2.0	1.088	0.199
Q4	30	2.73	2.0	1.530	0.279
Overall Perceived Manipulation	30	2.42	2.38	0.621	0.113

Table 5 shows that question number 04, which is "If you were alone, do you think you would have made the same decision?" has a mean of $\bar{x}=2.73$ ($SD=1.530, SE=0.279$). This is followed by question number 02, “How much do you think your decision was influenced by other’s opinions in the group?” with a mean of $\bar{x}=2.47$ ($SD=1.074, SE=0.196$). Then, the mean of question number 03, which is “Did you notice any non-verbal behaviours (e.g., body language, facial expressions) from others that affected your choice?” is $\bar{x} = 2.30$ ($SD=1.088, E=0.199$). Lastly, question number 01 asks, “To what extent did you feel pressure to agree with the group?” with a mean of $\bar{x}=2.17$ ($SD=0.986, SE=0.180$). Each question was answered by $N=30$ participants. Overall, the participants showed a low level of perceived manipulation ($\bar{x}=2.42, SD=0.621, SE=0.113$) since the results presented a mean of less than 3.39. Suggesting that participants were minimally influenced by external assertive factors.

Discussion

Love Issue

The results of the study indicate that participants' initial decision-making preferences were relatively balanced, with sixteen participants choosing "The One Who Loves Me" and fourteen participants choosing "The One I Love." After exposure to assertive social influence during group discussions, some participants changed their answers: seven shifted from "The One Who Loves Me" to "The One I Love," while another seven shifted in the opposite direction. Despite these individual changes, the overall distribution of responses remained unchanged. The Chi-Square Goodness-of-Fit test further confirmed that there was no statistically significant difference between the observed and expected responses. These findings suggest that participants' assertive social influence did not significantly affect participants' decision-making regarding the love issue.

The result may be explained by one of this study's limitations, which is the participants' psychological characteristics, specifically their self-esteem. The researchers did not first measure the participants' confidence levels, which could have helped the researchers understand the natural level of certainty the participants have in their decisions, allowing the researchers to compare the before and after intervention, which might have assisted them in isolating the effect of assertive social influence in the confidence shift of the participants. Consequently, the results revealed no significant difference between the observed and expected answers, indicating that participants may be confident in their responses, despite the confederates' emphasis on the opposite perspective of the majority's view. This is consistent with what Lee and Chung (2022) discussed; higher self-esteem is associated with greater resistance to social influence, indicating less likelihood to conform to others' opinions, since they are more confident in their own judgments. In contrast, individuals with low self-esteem showed a significant conformity rate compared to individuals with high self-esteem (Franzén & Mäder, 2023).

Another factor is the participants' firmness. They were asked to respond to the topic "The One I Love or The One Who Loves Me" and discuss their answers. The majority of the participants stood firm in their initial responses, with some participants presenting counterarguments to the confederates. This exchange of ideas resulted in a variety of perspectives and information. According to Sunstein (2002), as cited by Mittal et al. (2024), such situations promote critical thinking and the expression of dissenting viewpoints. This reduces conformity rates as participants are inclined to maintain their original beliefs even with the presence of assertive confederates. In addition, Capuano & Chekroun (2024) explained that in situations where group norms are uncertain, the existence of dissent and dialogue strengthens individual convictions while decreasing the likelihood of conforming.

In the context of Filipino culture, one potential reason for this result is the strong inclination of Filipinos toward collectivism (Rungduin et al., 2020). During the group discussion, the participants gave brief introductions and exchanged initial responses. The participants shared similar initial answers, which reinforces the establishment of group norms. This contributed to the value of *pakikisama* (getting along with others), a key cultural trait among Filipinos that emphasizes maintaining interpersonal harmony and togetherness. This cultural tendency likely explains the participants' strong predisposition to align with the group's opinions despite the assertions of the two confederates. According to Tablan (2023), individuals frequently align their opinions with the majority to avoid conflict, reinforcing collective decision-making. Similarly, as Cukur et al. (2004), quoted by Alampay (2024), noted, higher levels of collectivism are associated with valuing tradition and group conformity, which helps to explain the preference of group harmony over individual assertiveness.

Obligation Issue

The findings of the study showed that the majority of the participants initially answered "Yes," with the number of seventeen participants, and thirteen of them answered "No." After the exposure to assertive social influence during the group discussion, some participants shifted their answers, as three participants changed from "Yes" to "No" and two participants shifted from "No" to "Yes." Despite the observed changes in their answers, the overall distribution of responses remained consistent, with the Chi-Square

Goodness of Fit test showing that there is no statistically significant difference between the observed and expected responses. These findings suggest that the presence of assertive social influence did not significantly influence the participants' decision-making regarding the obligation issue.

These results may be explained by the role that confidence plays in making decisions in social settings. According to the previous study conducted by Cahyaningsih & Dewi (2019), conformity is driven by pessimism, lack of confidence, and the fear of being perceived as different. Individuals with lower confidence are more likely to fit in with the social environment to gain a sense of acceptance and reassurance. Moreover, Zheng et al. (2019) reported that there is a negative correlation between conformity rates and confidence, as people with lower confidence are more prone to conform to opposing views. As cited by Zheng et al. ((2019), the study conducted by Morgan (2012) aligns with their findings, which showed that people who lack confidence in their initial judgment are more likely to change their decisions.

Another potential factor that may have influenced the results is the generational changes in perspective about family responsibilities. According to recent studies, younger generations, including Millennials and Generation Z, are shifting traditional familial responsibilities and expectations. A study conducted by Bersamina & Hermosa (2024) on Filipino family dynamics showed that different levels of commitment to traditional values and practices are connected to modern family structures that are influenced by urbanization and changing societal norms. The evolution of these family structures and values may also contribute to a more uniform view among the respondents regarding the children's obligation to their families, regardless of the levels of assertiveness of an individual. This aligns with Garikapati et al. (2016), cited by Karna et al. (2023), that millennials are a generation in a transition that is changing social norms surrounding important life events.

Level of Perceived Manipulation Among Participants

The result shows that question number 04, which is “If you were alone, do you think you would have made the same decision?” has the highest mean among the survey. It has a mean of $\bar{x}=2.73$ ($SD=1.530$, $SE=0.279$). The majority of the participants, nine out of thirty (30%), answered, “Definitely not,” which indicates that the participants would have made a completely different decision. This finding suggests that when individuals are in a group, they are more likely to comply or change their judgments. It implies that social factors, such as peer influence or the desire to conform to group standards, had an important part in influencing the participants' decisions. Research by Crivelli & Balconi (2023) revealed that making decisions within a group often involves shared emotional and mental processes. These findings indicate that the need to conform to the group members' perspectives plays a crucial role in influencing actions, even when individual preferences differ.

This is followed by question number 02: “How much do you think your decision was influenced by other's opinions in the group?” with a mean of $\bar{x}= 2.47$ ($SD=1.074$, $SE=0.196$). This time, thirteen out of thirty (43.33%) mainly answered “slightly,” which suggests that the participants experienced minimal influence. This indicates that the decisions made by the participants were made with relatively little reliance on the external factor, which was the exposure to assertive influence. To support this, one study by Garcia et al. (2021) examines how group decisions were impacted by normative (social pressure) and informational (persuasion through information) factors, which suggested a result of a different degree of impact despite being exposed to an assertive social influence. In particular, the study shows that many people stand with their initial decisions even when exposed to assertive social influence, proving that the impact of a strong social influence can be limited.

Then, question number 03 stated, “Did you notice any non-verbal behaviours (e.g., body language, facial expressions) from others that affected your choice?” has a mean score of $\bar{x}=2.30$ ($SD=1.088$, $SE=0.199$). The leading answer to whom ten out of thirty participants (33.33%) responded is choice number 2 which stated, “Yes, but minimally,” which suggests that some non-verbal cues were observed but had minimal impact. Meaning that these cues were not strongly influential to the point that it did not affect the participants' decision-making processes. Burgoon et al. (2021) stated in their study about how non-verbal

cues can influence decision-making in a group setting that while these cues might provide information about one's sentiments or views, their influence on individual decision-making is frequently limited and varies by individual. According to the study, many people may detect these signals but fail to act on them.

Coming after is question number 01, which asked, "To what extent did you feel pressure to agree with the group?" with the mean of $\bar{x} = 2.17$ ($SD=0.986$, $SE=0.180$). Thirteen out of thirty participants (43.33%) mostly answered "A little," indicating that the pressure they perceived was minimal. This means that while their decisions were somewhat influenced by their exposure to assertion, the influence was not intense. This is supported by the study of Reale et al. (2023), which emphasized that despite external variables, such as assertive influence, there might be an impact on decision-making. However, the extent of that impact can differ. Furthermore, the result of the study showed that people retain some degree of autonomy in their decision-making processes, implying that while exposure to assertive instances influences choices, it does not necessarily result in significant or final changes in their choices.

Overall, the participants showed a low level of perceived manipulation ($\bar{x} = 2.42$, $SD=0.621$, $SE=0.113$) since the results presented a mean of less than 3.39. This might suggest that participants might have observed only minimal feelings of manipulation within the group setting, which suggests that, while some influences were present, the majority of the participants did not believe it to be strong. A 2024 study by Olckers and Walsh examined several methods for understanding how manipulation takes place in peer interactions and group dynamics. It talks about how people frequently see manipulation at low levels, especially in situations where social influences are present but not very powerful. The results indicated that although they may acknowledge some degree of social influence, they usually do not consider it to be significant.

Another reason would be the participants showing a high degree of autonomy despite their exposure to verbal and non-verbal cues. A study by Ruiz & Yabot (2024) suggests that participants often exercise their personal agency and make decisions on their own despite other influences, which implies that people can experience social influence without compromising their individuality.

The study's findings contradict the Social Influence Theory of Herbert Kelman. The minimal change in responses suggests that participants were not influenced by the assertive social presence, possibly due to the collective nature of group discussions. Participants may have valued group cohesion and alignment with shared perspectives that were consistent with their initial decisions, reducing the likelihood of them changing their answers. In the study of Lin et al. (2021), when individuals see that their answers are congruent with those of the group, it carries a rewarding message that leads to positive feelings and encourages individuals to maintain their initial selection. These findings contradict the theory's prediction that assertive influence could lead to at least temporary compliance, especially in contexts involving group discussions.

Furthermore, the lack of noticeable influence may indicate that participants were less likely to change their opinions when the viewpoints presented during the conversation went against their pre-existing beliefs or cultural standards. Dai et al. (2022) referenced Moussaïd et al. (2013) as saying that people showed a strong bias towards their original opinions and were reluctant to analyse the social information thoroughly. According to Oh et al. (2024), people also have a tendency to ignore competing viewpoints and focus more on the information that supports their preconceived notions. Consequently, whereas participants' opinions on the obligation problem were influenced by strongly held ideas about family and societal responsibilities, their answers to the love question were probably influenced by personal and emotional convictions.

Limitations

The study focused on first-year university students and was designed to examine the influence of assertive individuals on decision-making. However, there are several limitations that need to be acknowledged. Due to the study's relatively small sample size, the findings may be limited in their generalizability to a

broader population. Moreover, the preferential question that was utilized can distort the responses of the participants, making it difficult to tell whether the results were due to the presence of assertive individuals or due to the preferential question itself. In addition, the confidence level of the participants was not measured in this study, which could have been a variable in understanding the decision-making behaviour. Another limitation is the limited demographic of participants; this lack of diversity, particularly the absence of participants from different generations, reduces the applicability of the findings across the varying age groups. Finally, the confederates present during the experimentation were not as assertive as they should have been. These limitations emphasize the need for future research to address these constraints.

Recommendations

The findings of this study lead to several recommendations, such as utilizing a questionnaire that measures the confidence level of an individual so that it can avoid extraneous variables, like how high or low their confidence level is when making decisions. In addition, future research could look into evaluating the impact of Filipino cultural values like *pakikisama* on decision-making in order to better understand how the desire to maintain group cohesiveness impacts individual reactions to social dynamics. Moreover, future studies could include participants from several generations to account for differing views, making findings more inclusive and reflective of other generations' points of view. Not only these, but future researchers could also use another way of formulating the preferential questions to ensure that the assertive social influence is due to the confederates and not to the question generated. Finally, future studies should involve a larger number of participants to enhance the accuracy of the collected data.

Conclusion

The first-year student respondents were assessed using a two-item preferential test, namely: "The One I Love or The One Who Loves Me" (Love Issue) and "Do children have an obligation to give back to their family? Yes or No" (Obligation Issue). On the love issue, the initial responses showed that sixteen out of thirty participants (53.33%) chose "The One Who Loves Me," while the remaining fourteen participants (46.67%) preferred "The One I Love." On the other hand, on the obligation issue, seventeen out of thirty participants (56.67%) selected "Yes," whereas thirteen of the participants (43.33%) picked "No." As per the final responses on the love issue, seven out of sixteen participants who chose "The One Who Loves Me" changed their answers to "The One I Love," while the remaining nine participants stood with their initial response. Moreover, seven out of fourteen participants who initially answered "The One I Love" shifted their answers to "The One Who Loves Me." Overall, fourteen out of thirty participants showed changes in their initial and final responses.

Furthermore, the difference between the initial and final responses was determined using the Chi-Square Test, which resulted in a p-value of 0.732 for the love issue and a p-value of 0.869 for the obligation issue. This means that there is no significant difference between the initial and final responses of the participants despite the presence of assertive confederates, given that the two p-values are more than the significance level (0.05). Lastly, the participants exhibit a low level of perceived manipulation ($\bar{x} = 2.42$, $SD = 0.621$, $SE = 0.113$).

The findings suggest that when exposed to external pressures, people remain reasonably stable in their views. This resilience emphasizes the need to understand the underlying causes of personal actions for applications in psychology, education, and beyond. Future research might build on these findings by studying how assertive social influence affects decision-making in various cultural and situational circumstances.

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